

Informative Translation and its Language Features

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Abstract: Both the theoretical and practical elements of translation studies are addressed by the science of translation. The goal of translation theory is to theoretically describe the phenomenon of translation.

In the linguistic theory of translation, contact between communicants who speak different languages is established through translation as a sort of voice communication. The implications of this theory basis is macrolinguistics, which includes all of its new branches, including psycholinguistics, sociolinguistics, text linguistics, communicative linguistics, etc.

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Generally speaking, translators have two options for translating: direct translation, often known as literal translation, and oblique translation. In some translation tasks, it might be possible to translate the message from the source language into the target language element by element because it is based on parallel categories (in which case we can speak of structural parallelism) or parallel concepts (which are the result of metalinguistic parallelism). However, translators may also spot “lacunae” – gaps in the target language – that need to be filled in with comparable words or phrases in order to maintain consistency between the two messages. However, it is also possible that certain stylistic effects cannot be transferred into the target language without disrupting the lexis or the syntactic order due to structural or metalinguistic incompatibilities. In this situation, it is accepted that more complicated methods must be used. These techniques, known as oblique translation approaches may initially seem strange but can give translators tight control over the accuracy of their work. The next listing has oblique procedures after the first three direct ones.

Direct methods of translating: Borrowing (transcription, transliteration, and transcoding). Borrowing is the simplest approach of all translations for filling a gap, typically a metalinguistic one (such as a new technical procedure or unidentified notion). It wouldn't even be worth talking about in this context if translators didn't occasionally need to employ it to achieve a stylistic effect. For instance foreign terminology might be used in order to provide a translation with a sense of the culture of the source language.

Loan translation. Loan translation (calque) is a unique type of borrowing in which a language takes an expressive form from another but then literally translates each of its components.

As a result, the language either gains a new method of expression through a lexical loan or a structural loan, which adds a new construction to the language while maintaining the syntactic structure of the target text. The following borrowing categories can be distinguished:

loan words properly - words taken from a different language and assimilated to a certain degree;

loan translation –1) (Process) borrowing by literally translating words (often one portion after another) or word combinations, or by modeling terms after foreign patterns; 2) (result) Translation loans

(calques) - words and idioms created from material already in the English language but using literal word patterns from another language by the way of word-for-word or morpheme-for-morpheme translation.

semantic borrowings/loans – The phrase refers to the establishment of a new meaning in an English word as a result of the influence of a closely comparable word in another language.

Translation loans are literal translations of specific foreign words or idioms, word for word (or morpheme for morpheme). The phrase “to take the bull by the horns” (Latin), “fair sex” (French), “living space” (German), etc., are examples of phrases where the idea has been borrowed from a foreign language but is conveyed using native lexical units. Early in the Old English era, several Latin translation loans entered English, such as Sunday (solis dies). There are translational borrowings from Indian languages, including “pipe of peace,” “pale-faced,” “masterpiece,” “homesickness,” and “superman” from German.

Literal translation. Literal translation, sometimes known as word-for-word translation, is the direct conversion of a source text into a text in the target language that is grammatically and idiomatically suitable with the translator’s sole responsibility which is being to adhere to the linguistic rules of the text.

Translators must use oblique translation techniques if, after attempting the first three procedures, they feel that a literal translation is unsuitable. When a message is considered unacceptable, it must either: give a different meaning when translated literally; have no meaning at all; be structurally impossible; lack a corresponding expression in the target language’s metalinguistic experience; or have a corresponding expression but not in the same register.

Oblique translation. These translation strategies are used when an intellectual or structural aspects of the language cannot be translated directly into another language. That is both the source language and the target language in this instance. A translator should utilize the most appropriate oblique translation approaches if a word cannot be translated into the target language without changing the content or meaning of a statement. The oblique translation strategies include transposition, modulation, reformulation or equivalence, adaptation, and compensation.

1. Transposition. This method changes the order in which the pieces of speech are processed when they are translated to a target language. Although it has an impact on spoken meaning, the translation is not exact word for word. It might be described as shifting the word to preserve the meaning of the original language. This is usually common if the language pair is English and French. Transposition is the ideal translation method to use because these two languages cannot be directly translated word for word while preserving the original meaning. This is because English and French have different grammatical structures.

2. Modulation. This is a method that makes sure the translation provides the identical meaning in both languages through utilizing phrases that differ but provide the same meaning and context in a statement. These strategies alter the semantics of the source language and frequently affect its point of view. The translator can use this strategy to adjust the original or intended point of view and thought process while still keeping the message and not introducing a new component that may be strange or awkward to the target reader. It can be used within the same language as well as in conjunction with other languages.

3. Reformulation or Equivalence. This is a strategy commonly utilized by translators when they come across expressions that cannot be translated directly into other languages since doing so would affect their original meaning. The translator must express a message in a different way when using this technique. It is a difficult process since you must be fluent in both languages in order to know what to substitute for any expression or advertisement slogan when translating it to a target language. The process is inventive, but not necessarily simple. This is one strategy that I can assure you that translators dislike using because it is quite easy to complicate things using this technique.

4. *Adaptation*. This is a strategy, as the name implies, that permits the adaption of terms familiar in multiple languages that have the same meaning in another language. What we mean by adaptation is when something that is distinctive to one language culture is expressed in a different form that is familiar or appropriate to another language and culture. It represents a complete transformation in terms of cultural and environmental factors. If not used with someone who is interested and knows what they are doing, this strategy may not provide the greatest answer to a problem. When a circumstance in the source culture does not exist in the target culture, the cultural reference must be changed.

5. *Compensation*. You should be able to understand the compensation technique in the same manner you understand the meaning of the word compensation. This is a tactic employed when something cannot be translated and the lost meaning is compensated for elsewhere in the statement to make it make sense. A wide range of language pairs benefit from the compensatory strategy.

All of these strategies are useful for translators in a variety of situations. Depending on the issue you face as a translation, you should be able to determine which technique will be most effective in delivering correctly translated materials.

References.

1. Yunusovna K. L. PROBLEMS OF INTRODUCING INNOVATIVE TECHNOLOGIES IN THE LEARNING PROCESS IN A FOREIGN LANGUAGE //Gospodarka i Innowacje. – 2022. – Т. 28. – С. 127-129.
2. Khusainova L. Y., Khusainova I. U. SOME PRINCIPLES OF MODERN METHODS OF TEACHING ENGLISH LANGUAGE //British View. – 2022. – Т. 7. – №. 2.
3. Mukhtarova A., Klicheva A., Khusainova L. Y. THE ROLE OF INTERACTIVE TECHNOLOGIES IN LEARNING ENGLISH //International Conference on Research Identity, Value and Ethics. – 2022. – С. 459-461.
4. Абдувакилова М., Мавлонова Ш., Хусаинова Л. Ю. ПРЕИМУЩЕСТВО ОБУЧЕНИЯ ИНОСТРАННОМУ ЯЗЫКУ ЧЕРЕЗ ИНТЕРНЕТ //International Conference on Research Identity, Value and Ethics. – 2022. – С. 449-453.
5. Yunusovna K. L. et al. Inflation and Its Socio-Economic Impact //Kresna Social Science and Humanities Research. – 2022. – Т. 3. – С. 140-143.
6. Yunusovna K. L. et al. Structure of Foreign Investments in Uzbekistan //Kresna Social Science and Humanities Research. – 2022. – Т. 3. – С. 102-109.
7. Khusainova Leyla, Mamatkulova Komila. (2021). Communicative Competence and Ways to Reach it in Teaching Foreign Languages. Annals of the Romanian Society for Cell Biology, 7098–7109.
8. Хусаинова, Л. Жизнь, посвященная науке / Л. Хусаинова // Ватандаш. – 2015. – № 11(230). – С. 42-44.
9. Хусаинова, Л. Ю. Использование различных видов группового тренинга как формы обучения иностранным языкам / Л. Ю. Хусаинова, О. Ш. ў. л. Жумакулов // Архивариус. – 2021. – Т. 7. – № 2(56). – С. 42-45.
10. Khusainova, L. Yu. Method of teaching foreign languages using technical equipment / L. Yu. Khusainova // Archivarius. – 2020. – No 3(48). – P. 36-41.
11. Хусаинова, Л. Ю. Организация управления персоналом в системе развития туризма / Л. Ю. Хусаинова, С. Б. Кипчакова // Студенческий вестник. – 2019. – № 9-1(59). – С. 5-7.
12. L. Yu., Khusainova, 2021. About some reserves for improving the effectiveness of teaching foreign languages. [online] Thematicsjournals.in. Available at: <http://thematicsjournals.in/index.php/tje/article/view/801>

13. Khusainova L.Yu. (2021). Modern innovative technologies of teaching. *American Journal of Research*, 5(5-6, May-June), 23–28. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5288913>
14. Хусаинова, Л. and Маматкулова, К., 2021. О проблемах художественного перевода. *О‘ЗБЕК TILI TARAQQIYOTI VA XALQARO HAMKORLIK MASALALARI*, 1(1), pp.159-162.
15. Хусаинова, Л., 2021. Проблемы внедрения инновационных технологий в учебный процесс по иностранному языку для подготовки кадров сферы туризма. Республиканская 33-междисциплинарная дистанционная онлайн-конференции на тему "Научно-практические исследования в Узбекистане", 33(9), pp.30-32.
16. Хусаинова, Л., 2020. Разработка новых методических принципов для подготовки специалистов. *"Сервис" илмий-амалий журнал*, 4(1), pp.190-192.